

**INDIVIDUAL DIFFERENCES IN EPISTEMICALLY SUSPECT BELIEFS:
THE ROLE OF ANALYTIC THINKING AND SUSCEPTIBILITY TO COGNITIVE
BIASES**

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ABSTRACT

The endorsement of epistemically suspect (i.e., paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific) beliefs is widespread and has negative real-life consequences. Therefore, it is important to understand the reasoning processes – such as lower analytic thinking and susceptibility to cognitive biases – that might lead to the adoption of such beliefs. In two studies, I constructed and tested a novel questionnaire on epistemically suspect beliefs (Study 1, $N = 263$), and used it to examine probabilistic reasoning biases and belief bias in syllogistic reasoning as predictors of the endorsement of those beliefs, while accounting for analytic thinking and worldview variables (Study 2, $N = 397$). Probabilistic reasoning biases, analytic thinking, religious faith, and political liberalism consistently predicted various epistemically suspect beliefs, whereas the effect of syllogistic belief bias was largely restricted to pseudoscientific beliefs. Further research will be needed to examine the role the biased evaluation of evidence plays in the endorsement of epistemically suspect beliefs.

Keywords: epistemically suspect beliefs; probabilistic reasoning biases; belief bias in syllogistic reasoning; analytic thinking; individual differences

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, we have witnessed unprecedented developments in technology and science, which one might think would lead to a better understanding of the world around us. In spite of this progress, many people still seem to believe in things that contradict common naturalistic conceptions of the world and things that are either unsupported or disproved by modern science. Such epistemically suspect beliefs (ESBs; Pennycook, Cheyne, et al., 2015; Pennycook, Fugelsang, et al., 2015) comprise a wide category that encompasses beliefs in paranormal phenomena, conspiracy theories, and pseudoscientific claims. Importantly, these beliefs are surprisingly prevalent (e.g., Jensen, 2013; Mancosu et al., 2017) and have been linked to important negative real-life outcomes in domains such as health behaviour (Browne et al., 2015; Čavojová, Šrol, & Ballová Mikušková, 2020) or science denial (Lewandowsky, Gignac, et al., 2013). For these reasons, it is hugely important that we grasp the links between various types of epistemically suspect beliefs, discover the individual difference predictors, and examine their relationships with systematic reasoning and decision-making errors studied under the heuristics and biases research tradition (Pennycook, Fugelsang, et al., 2015b; Rizeq et al., 2020; Stanovich et al., 2016).

To this end, I will examine whether people who are more susceptible to various probabilistic reasoning biases and belief bias in syllogistic reasoning exhibit higher endorsement of paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific beliefs. Previous research has already demonstrated the link between probabilistic reasoning biases, syllogistic belief bias, and the endorsement of certain ESBs, mostly related to belief in paranormal phenomena (Brotherton & French, 2014; Dagnall et al., 2014; Rogers et al., 2009; Stanovich et al., 2016). I will extend this research by examining the associations between cognitive biases and a more diverse set of epistemically suspect beliefs, while also accounting for a wide range of analytic thinking indicators as well as several worldview and demographic factors previously shown to consistently predict the endorsement of such beliefs (e.g., Čavojová et al., 2020; Lobato et al., 2014; Ståhl & van Prooijen, 2018; Stanovich et al., 2016; Swami et al., 2014). Also, given the relative lack of psychometrically validated instruments specifically intended to measure individual differences in the endorsement of all three commonly recognized types of epistemically suspect beliefs, a secondary aim of the present study will be to develop and test a novel measure of paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific belief endorsement.

Epistemically suspect beliefs: dimensionality and association with analytic thinking

While paranormal phenomena, conspiracy theories, and pseudoscience may appear, at face value, to be three relatively distinct dimensions of ESBs, the available empirical evidence consistently shows that their endorsement is moderately to strongly correlated (e.g., Lobato et al. 2014; Stanovich et al. 2016; Bensley et al. 2019; Fasce and Picó 2019a; Čavoјová et al. 2020). A recent study by Rizeq et al. (2020), employing a confirmatory factor analysis, produced further evidence of the commonalities between the three dimensions of epistemically suspect beliefs. In that study, such beliefs were best conceptualized as three correlated general factors – representing paranormal, conspiracy, and anti-science beliefs – with several domain-specific dimensions for particular facets of paranormal beliefs (i.e., superstition, precognition, psi, and spiritualism).

Moreover, shared cognitive predictors play a role in the strong interrelationships among various types of ESBs. It has long been recognized that people’s tendency to engage in intuitive or analytic thinking plays an important role in the endorsement of different ESBs (e.g., Swami et al. 2014; Pennycook, Fugelsang, et al. 2015; Risen 2016). In line with this, many empirical studies show that various analytic thinking indicators are correlated with paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific beliefs. Indeed, analytic and intuitive thinking dispositions have repeatedly been shown to be among the most consistent cognitive predictors in this regard (Lindeman & Aarnio, 2006, 2007; Pennycook, Fugelsang, et al., 2015; Stanovich et al., 2016; Svedholm & Lindeman, 2013). Furthermore, evidence suggests that both general cognitive ability and more specific abilities such as cognitive reflection, numeracy, and scientific reasoning are also related to various forms of ESBs (Čavoјová et al., 2020; Pennycook, Cheyne, et al., 2015; Ståhl & van Prooijen, 2018; Stanovich et al., 2016). Together, these analytic thinking indicators seem to represent the key cognitive dispositions that underlie the adoption and maintenance of paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific beliefs.

The role of epistemically suspect beliefs in reasoning about complex issues

Although there are many definitions of rational thinking, a pervasive account in psychology and cognitive science rests on the distinction between instrumental and epistemic rationality (Stanovich et al., 2016). Instrumental rationality entails behaving in a way that best achieves our goals. Research in this area has therefore often focused on various systematic errors, i.e., cognitive biases, in reasoning and decision making. Epistemic rationality mainly concerns beliefs and how accurately they reflect the world around us (Evans, 2014), and thus is closely

related to the concept of epistemically suspect beliefs¹. These two types of rationality are, of course, intimately related in real-life: if we want to make decisions about important topics that best suit our needs, we need to possess unbiased information about those issues. This type of stored knowledge or rule, which may be needed to facilitate the reasoning process, is collectively termed mindware (Stanovich et al., 2008; 2016). Even though mindware is often viewed as a relatively narrow set of logical and mathematical skills implicated in solving reasoning tasks, it also includes the abilities to evaluate arguments, critical and scientific reasoning (Stanovich et al., 2011), and other knowledge structures needed to accurately reason about complex issues, such as risky health choices or climate change (Rizeq et al., 2020).

Conversely, contaminated mindware refers to “beliefs that may be unhelpful and that may inhibit the reasoning process” (Rizeq et al., 2020, p. 1). Unsurprisingly, the three key dimensions of contaminated mindware – anti-science attitudes, superstitious thinking, and conspiracy beliefs (Stanovich et al., 2016) – correspond to the three main types of epistemically suspect beliefs. Many studies show how various types of contaminated mindware may inhibit our ability to reason about complex topics. For example, belief in conspiracy theories predicts rejection of scientific findings on climate change (Lewandowsky, Oberauer, et al., 2013) and vaccinations (Lewandowsky, Gignac, et al., 2013), and conspiracy mentality has been proposed as one of the key mechanisms in the motivated rejection of scientific evidence in general (Lewandowsky & Oberauer, 2016). Lack of scientific reasoning, on the other hand, has been associated with higher belief in alternative and complementary medicine (Čavojová & Ersoy, 2019), as well as with anti-vaccination attitudes, and the endorsement of COVID-19 conspiracy beliefs and rejection of the coronavirus vaccine (Čavojová, Šrol, & Ballová Mikušková, 2020). Further evidence for the importance of having accurate mindware comes from studies that show associations between various ESBs and important negative real-life outcomes, such as risky health choices (Browne et al., 2015; Grebe & Natrass, 2012), political extremism (van Prooijen et al., 2015), justification and support for violence (Jolley & Paterson, 2020), or the tendency to perceive nonsensical bullshit statements as profound and even share them on social media (Čavojová et al., 2019; Pennycook, Cheyne, et al., 2015).

The relationship between epistemically suspect beliefs and reasoning is a complex one. All of the abovementioned evidence shows how contaminated mindware, in the form of paranormal,

¹ However, ESBs are also associated with instrumental rationality, as the endorsement of such beliefs may sometimes lead directly to actions that thwart our goals (Stanovich, 2016).

conspiracy, and pseudoscientific beliefs, shapes our ability to reason about important topics and may therefore lead to suboptimal choices with serious consequences. Yet various reasoning processes have also been shown to contribute to the endorsement of ESBs (Rizeq et al., 2020). Specifically, there is evidence that two broad types of reasoning processes – probabilistic reasoning biases and biased evaluation of evidence – play a role in the endorsement of some epistemically suspect beliefs.

Probabilistic reasoning biases and belief bias in syllogistic reasoning as predictors of ESBs

It has been suggested that similar cognitive mechanisms may underlie the susceptibility to cognitive biases and ESBs. The tendency to process information analytically, which plays an important role in the adoption and maintenance of ESBs, is also a crucial component of the ability to avoid engaging in biased reasoning (Pennycook, Fugelsang, et al., 2015). Furthermore, Risen (2016) argues that intuitive operations, such as the representativeness heuristic that underlies many biases in probabilistic reasoning, and the evaluation of evidence biased by one's previous beliefs, may not simply be responsible for the acquisition of some unwarranted beliefs but may also be the reason why such beliefs are exceptionally hard to amend once the person endorses them (see also Rizeq et al., 2020). The role of these biased intuitive processes in the adoption and maintenance of some ESBs mirrors two dominant earlier accounts – biased probability judgment and selective bias hypothesis – which were formulated to explain the surprisingly high prevalence of paranormal beliefs (e.g., Blackmore & Trościanko, 1985; Dagnall, Parker, & Munley, 2007).

According to the biased probability judgment hypothesis, people may adopt paranormal and conspiracy beliefs because they interpret coincidental events, such as breaking a mirror and having bad luck later that day, as being mutually associated or causally connected, owing to their biased perception of probability (Blackmore & Trościanko, 1985; van der Wal et al., 2018). Building on this assumption, studies have shown that performance on various tasks related to probabilistic reasoning biases, including conjunction fallacy (Brotherton & French, 2014; Rogers et al., 2009, 2016, 2017), base-rate neglect (Dagnall et al., 2014), ratio bias, and the gambler's fallacy (Stanovich et al., 2016), is associated with the endorsement of paranormal and conspiracy beliefs. Although pseudoscientific beliefs have rarely been examined in these studies (but see Stanovich et al., 2016), there is some evidence that their adoption could also be related to the biased perception of probability and the tendency to interpret causal connections between coincidental phenomena (Torres et al., 2020). Therefore, the present study

included pseudoscientific belief endorsement as well, in order to explore whether it shares similar associations with biased reasoning in probabilistic tasks, as do other types of epistemically suspect beliefs.

The second account, introduced to explain belief in the paranormal, proposed a selective bias mechanism according to which people who already hold some ESBs are more likely to look for evidence that confirms rather than confronts their beliefs, thus reinforcing their existing worldviews (Dagnall et al., 2007). Indeed, a long line of research shows how our own beliefs influence the kind of information we search for and how we interpret the arguments and evidence (e.g., Drummond & Fischhoff, 2019; Macpherson & Stanovich, 2007). One of the most frequently studied reasoning paradigms in this domain is syllogistic reasoning with belief bias. The research in this paradigm repeatedly shown that people's ability to reason with logical arguments is strongly inhibited when the arguments do not align with their existing knowledge or beliefs (e.g., Čavojová et al., 2018; Macpherson & Stanovich, 2007). While the potential role of belief bias in syllogistic reasoning has not yet received much attention in the research on ESBs, there is some evidence that people with high levels of paranormal and conspiracy beliefs, as well as antiscientific attitudes, exhibit higher susceptibility to belief bias (Stanovich et al., 2016; Svedholm & Lindeman, 2013).

It should be mentioned that although susceptibility to belief bias in syllogistic reasoning and to various probabilistic reasoning biases may appear to be two relatively distinct domains of rational thinking, they share similar underlying cognitive mechanisms (Stanovich et al., 2016). Normative reasoning in these two paradigms does of course depend on quite different mindware knowledge structures, e.g. knowledge of the rules of deductive inference insofar as syllogistic reasoning is concerned, or probabilistic and statistical knowledge such as the conjunction rule in probabilistic reasoning tasks. Besides the mindware component, however, one's motivation and ability to think analytically plays an important role in reasoning in both of the aforementioned paradigms (Stanovich et al., 2016). This is why analytic and intuitive thinking dispositions, as well as certain general and specific cognitive abilities, have repeatedly been shown to predict susceptibility to a variety of cognitive biases, such as those related to probabilistic and syllogistic reasoning (e.g. Klaczynski, 2014; Šrol & De Neys, 2020; Stanovich et al., 2016; Toplak, West, & Stanovich, 2011). Moreover, as has already been mentioned, these analytic thinking indicators are known to contribute to the endorsement of ESBs as well. For these reasons, the present study included a wide range of analytic thinking indicators, enabling us to disentangle the roles of analytic thinking, probabilistic reasoning

biases, and belief bias in syllogistic reasoning on the endorsement of paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific beliefs.

Present research

To summarize, the main goal of the present research was to bring novel evidence regarding the individual difference predictors of epistemically suspect beliefs (ESBs) and, crucially, to examine probabilistic reasoning biases, belief bias in syllogistic reasoning, and analytic thinking as predictors of the endorsement of paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific beliefs. To this end, I developed a novel ESB questionnaire consisting of paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific belief subscales, and initially tested its psychometric characteristics and associations with several probabilistic reasoning biases in Study 1. The motivation for developing this new questionnaire was threefold. First, while there are many inventories and scales available for measuring paranormal, conspiracy, or pseudoscientific beliefs, there are few instruments that have been specifically developed and psychometrically tested to measure all three key types of ESB (see also Rizeq et al., 2020). Secondly, the extant measures rarely include reverse-scored items and thus the responses to them may be influenced by acquiescence response bias – the tendency to respond affirmatively to all items regardless of their content (Watson, 1992). Finally, ESBs are known to be very culturally specific (e.g. Brotherton et al., 2013), therefore, researchers in this area may find it useful to have measurement instruments that have been tested and validated across various samples (the present study included both a Slovak sample and a multinational sample, primarily consisting of UK and US participants).

The second study served to confirm the psychometric structure of the ESB questionnaire observed in Study 1 and, crucially, to comprehensively examine the role of probabilistic reasoning biases and belief bias in syllogistic reasoning in the endorsement of epistemically suspect beliefs. Importantly, to extend the existing research on this issue, it was necessary to account for the role of the analytic thinking indicators – i.e., cognitive ability, analytic and intuitive thinking dispositions, cognitive reflection, numeracy, and scientific reasoning – that are thought to underlie the relationship between various cognitive biases and ESBs. These were therefore included in Study 2, in order to examine whether probabilistic reasoning biases and belief bias in syllogistic reasoning predict the endorsement of paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific beliefs over and above the analytic thinking indicators. Also, two simple measures of political liberalism and strength of religious faith were likewise included for this purpose, as these worldview indicators have been shown to substantially contribute to the

acceptance of ESBs (e.g., Lobato et al., 2014; Ståhl & van Prooijen, 2018). Thus, Study 2 was uniquely equipped to extend the previous research on individual differences in ESBs (e.g., Čavojová, Šrol, & Jurkovič, 2020; Lobato et al., 2014; Rizeq et al., 2020) by simultaneously examining a wide range of predictors of paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific belief endorsement, consisting of cognitive biases, analytic thinking indicators, worldview variables, and demographic factors.

STUDY 1

The aim of Study 1 was to construct and then test a novel ESB questionnaire by examining its psychometric structure via a confirmatory factor analysis and to scrutinize the results in order to identify items with low loadings on their respective factors, which could then be excluded to refine the subscales. The secondary goal was to initially confirm the correlations between paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific beliefs and three probabilistic reasoning biases, i.e. base-rate neglect, conjunction fallacy, and gambler's fallacy.

Participants

Three hundred and sixteen participants took part in Study 1; however, after excluding participants ($n = 53$) who incorrectly answered one or both attention check questions², the final sample consisted of 263 Slovak participants (117 male, 146 female) with an age range between 18 and 76 years ($M = 24.80$, $SD = 7.00$). Concerning education, 52.9% of participants reported having a college degree, 43.7% reported having finished high school with a diploma, and the rest had finished high school without a diploma (2.3%) or had finished a vocational school (1.1%). The sample size was not determined beforehand but was set to include as many people as would agree to participate in the study through online survey queries on social media in the time allocated for the data collection.

Materials

Epistemically suspect beliefs:

² Two attention check questions were included in the study. One was mixed in with the gambler's fallacy items and was constructed to resemble these tasks, but unlike the real items it did not involve a catch but required a very simple unambiguous correct response. The second one simply instructed participants to select the option "I completely agree" to check if they were paying attention.

I constructed a novel questionnaire that contained 38 items pertaining to paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific beliefs. Most of the items were taken from scales used to measure various ESBs in previous research (Brotherton, French, & Pickering, 2013; Halama, 2019; Lewandowsky et al., 2013; Lobato et al., 2014; Mancosu et al., 2017; Stone et al., 2018; Tobacyk, 2004), and the remainder were created by the author. The items were selected to cover a wide range of paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific beliefs and avoid culturally-specific knowledge (Brotherton et al., 2013). Both positively worded (e.g., “*Certain objects, such as rabbits’ feet and four-leaved clovers, genuinely bring luck*”) and negatively worded statements (e.g. “*There are no such things as ghosts*”) were selected to avoid acquiescence response bias (e.g. Watson, 1992).

The full wording of the items along with their average ratings can be found in Section A of the Supplementary Material. There were 12 items pertaining to paranormal beliefs, 12 items for conspiracy beliefs, and 14 items to measure pseudoscientific beliefs. Items from the three subscales were mixed up randomly on a single page and participants were asked to indicate their agreement with each of them using the same five-point response scale (1: “*completely disagree*”, 2: “*somewhat disagree*”, 3: “*neither agree nor disagree*”, 4: “*somewhat agree*”, 5: “*completely agree*”). Prior to the analyses, ratings of some items were recoded so that the higher scores always represented a greater acceptance of ESBs. The average rating for each subscale was used as the indicator of participants’ acceptance of paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific beliefs. Additionally, in some of the analyses, I combined the ratings for all the items to create a single epistemically suspect belief composite score (see below). The descriptive statistics pertaining to the paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific belief scales can be found in Table 1.

Heuristics and biases tasks:

Probabilistic reasoning biases. Three heuristics and biases tasks pertaining to probabilistic reasoning were used with four items for each task. These included *base-rate neglect* and *conjunction fallacy* problems, which tested whether participants based their judgments on prior probabilities (i.e., base-rates) and probabilistic rules (i.e., conjunction rule), or on appealing stereotypical anecdotal evidence (Tversky & Kahneman, 1974, 1983); and *the gambler’s fallacy* items designed to test people’s mistaken belief when judging random sequences that if one outcome occurs more often than usual for a period of time, it will be less likely to occur in the future and vice versa (Tversky & Kahneman, 1974). A more detailed description of

heuristics and biases tasks can be found in Section B of the Supplementary Material. All heuristics and biases tasks were scored such that higher values represent greater susceptibility to the respective cognitive bias. Average sums of biased answers were used as indicators of susceptibility to conjunction fallacy ($M = 2.76$, $SD = 1.26$, $\alpha = .63$), base-rate neglect ($M = 2.05$, $SD = 1.44$, $\alpha = .70$), and the gambler's fallacy ($M = 0.96$, $SD = 1.01$, $\alpha = .52$). In the analyses below, I will also use a probabilistic reasoning bias composite score, calculated as a regression score for the single component extracted from the principal component analysis with the scores of three probabilistic reasoning tasks (the analysis indicated a single component with an eigenvalue greater than one and 52% explained variance with high loadings of all three indicators).

Procedure

The study was run as an online survey. Participants were first presented with an informed consent form and then filled in their basic demographic information. The first block of study materials consisted of heuristics and biases tasks and the second one contained the ESB questionnaire. Prior to each type of reasoning task, participants were presented with thorough instructions to familiarize them with the task at hand.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Confirmatory factor analysis of the ESB questionnaire

Firstly, I examined the psychometric structure of the epistemically suspect belief questionnaire by running a confirmatory factor analysis with DWLS estimation. The analysis was performed in JASP software and *lavaan* package in R software (Rosseel, 2012). Two models were tested to examine the structure of epistemically suspect beliefs: a unidimensional model with all items loading on a single generic ESB latent factor; and a three-factor model where the items loaded on their three latent dimensions representing paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific beliefs. The results showed that the three-factor model fitted the data well, $\chi^2(662) = 758.69$, $p = .005$, CFI = .989, TLI = .989, RMSEA = .024. Although the fit of the one-factor model was good, $\chi^2(665) = 798.55$, $p < .001$, CFI = .985, TLI = .984, RMSEA = .028, it was significantly worse when compared with the three-factor model using a chi-square difference test, $\chi^2_{difference}(3) = 39.86$, $p < .001$. Therefore, the three-factor model was retained. However, the initial results showed ten items with relatively low standardized loadings ($< .40$), the exclusion

of which did not decrease the reliability (Cronbach's α) of their respective subscales. These were two items from paranormal beliefs, three on conspiracy theory, and five from the pseudoscience subscale (the original pool of 38 items is presented in Section A of the Supplementary Material). The ten items with low factor loadings were therefore excluded and the confirmatory factor analysis was rerun to see whether the exclusion led to the improved fit of the three-factor model whilst retaining high reliability of the three subscales and high correlations with the original longer scales.

After excluding the ten items, the model fit improved even further, $\chi^2(347) = 389.58, p = .057$, CFI = .994, TLI = .994, RMSEA = .022. The resulting three-factor model showed substantial loadings of every item on its respective factor. The mean endorsement and standardized factor loadings of each item along with the average endorsements and reliabilities of the three subscales of the resulting 28-item ESB questionnaire can be found in Table 1. As can be seen from the table, reliability estimates were adequate for each subscale: paranormal ($\alpha = .79$), conspiracy ($\alpha = .86$), and pseudoscientific beliefs ($\alpha = .79$). Additionally, the further exclusion of any other item would not have increased the reliability of any of the subscales. Importantly, the reduced scales had very high correlations with the original length scales (based on the initial 38 items) for the paranormal ($r = .98$), conspiracy ($r = .98$), and pseudoscientific belief subscale ($r = .96$), i.e., the refined and full-length scales shared 92–96% of their variance. The refined scales were used in all subsequent analyses as they showed good reliability and high standardized item loadings on the respective factors, as well as a very good fit under the three-factor model. Additionally, I calculated a single composite epistemically suspect belief score by averaging the 28-items from all three dimensions ($M = 2.19, SD = 0.65, \alpha = .92$). This composite score was examined in subsequent analyses along with specific results for paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific beliefs, as an additional indicator of the general propensity to endorse ESBs. The analyses of age and gender differences in the endorsement of ESBs can be found in Section F of the Supplementary Material.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics and psychometric properties of the 28-item ESB questionnaire in Study 1 and 2

	Study 1			Study 2		
	Mean (SD)	Endorsement rate	λ	Mean (SD)	Endorsement rate	λ
<i>Composite ESB scale</i> ($\alpha_{S1} = .92$; $\alpha_{S2} = .93$)	2.19 (0.65)	18.0%		2.32 (0.69)	22.4%	
<i>Paranormal subscale</i> ($\alpha_{S1} = .79$; $\alpha_{S2} = .88$)	2.11 (0.68)	18.0%		2.32 (0.83)	24.5%	
1. Creatures known popularly as Big Foot, the Loch Ness Monster, and/or the Chupacabra do not exist (R)	1.94 (1.23)	14.1%	.41	2.09 (1.14)	14.4%	.49
2. Extraterrestrial life forms have visited Earth and abducted human beings	1.78 (1.03)	6.4%	.46	2.09 (1.15)	14.4%	.69
3. Certain objects, such as rabbits' feet and four-leaved clovers, genuinely bring luck	1.50 (0.89)	3.4%	.48	1.77 (1.06)	10.3%	.69
4. The horoscope accurately tells a person's future	1.22 (0.60)	1.9%	.35	1.62 (1.02)	10.1%	.61
5. The Bermuda Triangle is a special location on the planet that, for some reason, causes ships and aircraft to crash or disappear more often than anywhere else on the planet	2.88 (1.45)	39.2%	.63	3.05 (1.31)	47.4%	.58
6. Geological objects, such as certain crystals, precious metals, or magnets, have intrinsic mystical properties	1.94 (1.17)	12.5%	.75	2.36 (1.24)	23.9%	.80
7. Some people who came close to death have genuine glimpses of afterlife	2.64 (1.29)	26.2%	.59	2.85 (1.28)	35.8%	.71
8. There are no such things as ghosts (R)	2.77 (1.51)	36.1%	.47	2.78 (1.38)	37.3%	.61
9. Full moon causes people to behave oddly	2.90 (1.28)	34.2%	.53	2.70 (1.36)	36.3%	.53
10. Some numbers and dates are more lucky or unlucky than others, such as Friday the 13th or the number 7	1.52 (0.95)	6.4%	.47	1.91 (1.19)	15.1%	.66
<i>Conspiracy subscale</i> ($\alpha_{S1} = .86$; $\alpha_{S2} = .88$)	2.14 (0.82)	16.7%		2.16 (0.84)	18.7%	
1. Groups of scientists manipulate, fabricate, or suppress evidence in order to deceive the public	2.70 (1.28)	28.5%	.60	2.79 (1.25)	33.8%	.64
2. Moon landings have never happened and the proofs have been fabricated by NASA and the US government	1.65 (1.03)	6.9%	.58	1.76 (1.11)	10.8%	.66
3. There is evidence of alien visitations on Earth, but governments keep it a secret	2.10 (1.24)	15.6%	.55	2.45 (1.28)	25.2%	.73
4. Members of the US government were involved in the planning and execution of the events that happened on 11 September 2001 (attack on the World Trade Center)	2.52 (1.24)	21.6%	.65	2.36 (1.31)	22.2%	.65
5. Exhaust seen in the sky behind airplanes is actually chemicals sprayed by the government for sinister reasons	1.41 (0.87)	3.8%	.58	1.54 (1.00)	8.3%	.64
6. Pharmaceutical industry is in league with the medical industry to "invent" new diseases in order to make money	2.50 (1.41)	26.6%	.81	2.36 (1.23)	23.4%	.70

7. The spread of certain viruses and/or diseases is the result of the deliberate, concealed efforts of some organization	2.24 (1.26)	16.7%	.70	2.27 (1.20)	19.6%	.80
8. Technology with mind-control capacities is used on people without their knowledge	2.46 (1.44)	24.7%	.63	2.28 (1.22)	19.6 %	.72
9. US astronauts have been to the moon (R)	1.66 (1.01)	6.1%	.54	1.60 (0.95)	5.8%	.44
<i>Pseudoscience subscale</i> ($\alpha_{S1} = .79$; $\alpha_{S2} = .80$)	2.32 (0.70)	19.2%		2.50 (0.68)	23.8%	
1. The variety of species of life that exist today is best explained by the scientific theory of evolution (R)	1.68 (1.04)	6.1%	.40	1.80 (1.08)	10.1%	.35
2. Homeopathic treatments are just as valid as traditional medical treatments for serious illnesses	1.99 (1.10)	7.6%	.64	2.47 (1.24)	23.9%	.73
3. There are many alternative methods which are effective for cancer treatment even though classical medicine does not approve of them	2.81 (1.49)	36.5%	.77	3.00 (1.26)	41.3%	.70
4. Reiki healing, otherwise known as Palm healing, is effective in healing the body	2.80 (1.31)	31.2%	.47	2.57 (1.20)	22.7%	.75
5. I believe that because there are so many unknowns, it is dangerous to manipulate the natural genetic material of foods	3.08 (1.30)	35.0%	.43	3.41 (1.14)	54.9%	.49
6. There is no evidence that currently used genetically modified crops (GMOs) can cause health problems (R)	3.29 (1.25)	44.8%	.47	3.01 (1.12)	34.8%	.37
7. Oral use of sodium chlorite solution (also known as Miracle Mineral Solution, or MMS) has beneficial effects on human organism	2.30 (1.04)	5.0%	.60	2.83 (0.80)	11.1%	.49
8. Childhood vaccines are one causal factor in the development of autism	1.59 (0.98)	4.6%	.59	1.95 (1.16)	13.1%	.60
9. Vaccination has made a major beneficial contribution to global health (R)	1.34 (0.74)	1.9%	.44	1.42 (0.71)	2.0%	.38

Note. The endorsement rate was calculated as a percentage of “somewhat agree” and “completely agree” responses (for reverse-scored items this was done after reverse coding, therefore, the endorsement rate actually reflects the rejection rate of those items). For the subscale composites, it was the average endorsement of all items in the respective subscale. Reverse scores items are marked (R). Column labelled “ λ ” shows standardized factor loadings of items on their respective factors extracted from the CFA analysis with DWLS estimation performed in JASP. All factor loadings are significant ($p < .001$).

Correlations between ESBs and probabilistic reasoning biases

I examined the correlations between probabilistic reasoning biases and the endorsement of paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific beliefs. As can be seen from Table 2, each type of epistemically suspect belief correlated positively with higher susceptibility to the gambler’s fallacy, base-rate neglect, and conjunction fallacy. The only exception was the association between the tendency to commit a conjunction fallacy and endorsement of conspiracy theories,

which was in the predicted direction but was not statistically significant. This stands in contrast to previous results by Brotherton and French (2014), who reported moderate correlations between conspiracy beliefs and the tendency to commit a conjunction fallacy in a variety of domains (tasks with neutral, conspiracy, and paranormal content). Yet there was also a slightly lower correlation between the tendency to commit base-rate neglect and conspiracy belief endorsement, in comparison with paranormal and pseudoscientific beliefs. This could suggest that people who believe conspiracy theories may not be as susceptible to biases in probabilistic reasoning as those who believe in paranormal phenomena and pseudoscience. Be that as it may, consistent with the biased probabilistic reasoning account, all three types of ESB were found to be associated with higher susceptibility to probabilistic reasoning biases in general (Dagnall et al., 2014; Rogers et al., 2009).

Table 2. Correlations between ESBs and probabilistic reasoning biases in Study 1

	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.
1. Paranormal beliefs	1						
2. Conspiracy beliefs	.69	1					
3. Pseudoscientific beliefs	.67	.73	1				
4. ESB composite	(.88)	(.91)	(.89)	1			
5. Conjunction fallacy	.21	.07	.18	.17	1		
6. Gambler's fallacy	.19	.21	.27	.25	.19	1	
7. Base-rate neglect	.26	.17	.29	.26	.39	.25	1
8. Probabilistic biases composite	.30	.20	.34	.31	(.75)	(.61)	(.79)

Note. Correlations are based on 263 observations. ESB: epistemically suspect belief. Correlations in parentheses indicate part-whole relationships. Correlations of $r > .13$ are significant at $p < .05$, $r > .16$ are significant at $p < .01$, and $r > .21$ are significant at $p < .001$. Correlations that appear in bold are significant ($p < .05$).

STUDY 2

The aim of Study 1 was to conduct a psychometric examination of the ESB questionnaire and to initially examine the correlations between probabilistic reasoning biases and the endorsement of paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific beliefs. The same questionnaire was then employed in Study 2, in order to conduct a thorough investigation of the role of probabilistic reasoning biases and belief bias in syllogistic reasoning in the endorsement of ESBs. To this end, this study included several syllogistic reasoning problems to measure belief bias – one aspect of the biased evaluation of evidence, which, it has been suggested, may be a

crucial reasoning mechanism for the adoption and maintenance of ESBs (Dagnall et al., 2007). Also, I extended the battery of probabilistic reasoning biases by including more items per task to improve their reliability, which Study 1 showed was relatively low, and one additional task which dealt with people's tendency to commit ratio bias in probabilistic reasoning. Finally, I also measured a wide range of analytic thinking indicators which were previously shown to be associated with both ESBs and the susceptibility to probabilistic reasoning biases and belief bias in syllogistic reasoning (e.g., Čavojová, Šrol, & Jurkovič, 2020; Stanovich et al., 2016). The inclusion of these factors made it possible to examine the extent to which analytic thinking indicators, probabilistic reasoning biases, and belief bias in syllogistic reasoning contribute to the endorsement of ESBs.

METHOD

Participants

Participants were recruited through Prolific, an online academic service, and paid £7.50 for their participation. In total, 405 participants completed the online study; however, eight failed to correctly answer more than one attention check question³ and were automatically excluded from all further analyses⁴. The final sample consisted of 397 participants (256 female, 140 male, 1 genderqueer) between 18 and 74 years old ($M = 36.07$, $SD = 12.47$). Most participants reported having a college degree (79%), the rest reported either having a high school / GED education (19%), or less than a high school education (2%). The sample size of 400 participants was determined beforehand based on the maximum number of participants I could afford to recruit given my research budget and the cost of Prolific workers. The post-hoc sensitivity analysis carried out in G*Power 3.1 software (Faul, Erdfelder, Lang, & Buchner, 2007) showed that this sample size should provide at least 80% statistical power with 5% error probability to detect any correlations of $r > .140$.

³ Three attention check questions were included in the study. Two of them were mixed in with the heuristics and biases problems and were constructed to resemble these tasks, but unlike the real items there was no catch involved just a very simple unambiguous correct response. The third one was presented among numeracy problems and simply instructed participants to select the option “none of the above”, thereby showing they had read the item.

⁴ Adopting the stricter criterion of answering all three attention check questions correctly would have led to the exclusion of a further 43 participants. However, excluding these participants would not have changed any of the main results presented in the mediation models predicting the endorsement of paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific beliefs (see below).

Materials

Epistemically suspect beliefs:

The ESB questionnaire was identical to the one used in Study 1. While the original questionnaire was administered in its entirety, here I analyze only the 28 items retained after the psychometric analysis presented in Study 1, containing ten items pertaining to paranormal beliefs, nine items to conspiracy beliefs, and nine items to pseudoscientific beliefs⁵. Again, the average rating for each subscale was used as an indicator of participants' acceptance of paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific beliefs, and the composite ESBs average rating from all 28 items was also used in some of the analyses below. The descriptive statistics and reliability estimates pertaining to the items of the paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific belief scales can be found in Table 1.

Heuristics and biases tasks:

Five heuristics and biases tasks were used and each task contained six items. A more detailed description of all the heuristics and biases tasks can be found in Section B of the Supplementary Material. All the heuristics and biases tasks were scored so that higher values represent greater susceptibility to the respective cognitive bias. The descriptive statistics for the heuristics and biases problems are presented in Table 3.

Belief bias in syllogistic reasoning. To examine the role of biased evaluation of evidence when faced with conflicting previous beliefs, I used belief bias in the syllogistic reasoning task (Stanovich et al., 2016). Each item included two premises and a conclusion, and participants had to evaluate the logical validity of the conclusions, which were always worded so their believability conflicted with their logical validity (i.e., valid-unbelievable or invalid-believable).

Probabilistic reasoning biases. Four tasks were used that represented various probabilistic reasoning biases. These included three tasks from Study 1 (i.e., base-rate neglect, conjunction fallacy, and the gambler's fallacy problems) and an additional *ratio bias* task (Stanovich & West, 2008), in which participants were presented with two jars with different ratios of red and

⁵ The preliminary exploration suggested that the ten items excluded after the psychometric analysis presented in Study 1 had consistently low loadings on their three respective factors in this sample, therefore, only 28 items were retained for the subsequent analyses pertaining to the endorsement of ESBs.

white marbles and had to choose the jar that maximized their chance of drawing a red marble. As in Study 1, besides the scores for the four individual probabilistic reasoning biases, I also used a probabilistic reasoning bias composite score – a regression score for the single component extracted from the principal component analysis with an eigenvalue greater than one and 45% explained variance with high loadings for all four indicators.

Table 3. Descriptives of heuristics and biases tasks, analytic thinking indicators, and political and religious beliefs

	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	α
Syllogistic belief bias	2.70	2.10	.84
Base-rate neglect	2.94	2.33	.88
Conjunction fallacy	3.99	2.06	.83
Ratio bias	1.57	1.70	.72
Gambler's fallacy	2.09	1.59	.63
Cognitive ability	5.03	2.97	.73
Cognitive reflection	5.07	2.40	.75
Numeracy	4.64	1.63	.51
Scientific reasoning	6.99	2.52	.68
Analytic thinking disposition	3.42	0.78	.78
Intuitive thinking disposition	3.81	0.68	.84
Political liberalism	4.73	1.37	–
Religious faith	2.33	1.88	–

Note. The table contains means, standard deviations, and reliability estimates (Cronbach's α) for the heuristics and biases tasks, analytic thinking indicators, and political and religious beliefs.

Analytic thinking indicators:

The descriptive statistics for analytic thinking indicators are presented in Table 3.

Cognitive ability. General cognitive ability was measured using the *Vienna matrix test* (VMT; Klose, Černočová, & Král, 2002), a 24-item measure of fluid intelligence similar to Raven's progressive matrices. However, to reduce participant fatigue owing to the length of the study, I used a shortened version of the test, which was based on the psychometric properties observed in previous research (Šrol, 2019). For this short version of VMT, 14 items were selected, which showed good composite reliability ($\alpha = .82$) and a very high correlation with the full version of the test ($r = .96$), based on data collected in the aforementioned study. Participants had 15 minutes to answer as many of the 14 problems as they could by choosing one of the eight response alternatives to complete a pattern in a complex figure. The sum of correctly answered problems was used as the measure of cognitive ability.

Cognitive reflection measure. Ten items designed to evoke compelling but wrong intuitive responses were used to measure cognitive reflection. Four items were taken from the work of Thomson and Oppenheimer (2016) and the six remaining problems were based on a cognitive reflection measure used by Šrol (2019). Correct answers to the ten problems were summed into a single cognitive reflection composite score.

Numeracy. Eight items were used to tap into participants' numerical ability. Half were taken from the *Berlin numeracy test* (Cokely, Galesic, Schulz, Ghazal, & Garcia-Retamero, 2012), and the other half from the measure used by Lipkus, Samsa, and Rimer (2001). The sum of correct responses on the eight items combined was used as the indicator of participants' numeracy. The resulting eight-item test proved to be of somewhat low internal consistency ($\alpha = .51$), however, it was retained as it showed meaningful and substantial relationships with other variables in the study (see below).

Scientific reasoning. Scientific reasoning ability was measured using the recently developed *Scientific Reasoning Scale* (SRS; Drummond & Fischhoff, 2017a). The scale consists of 11 short scenarios pertaining to people's understanding of basic scientific concepts, such as confounding variables, control group, and random assignment of participants to conditions. Each scenario is followed by a brief statement and participants are asked to indicate whether the statement is true or false. The sum of correctly answered items was used as the measure of participants' scientific reasoning ability.

Analytic and intuitive thinking disposition. I used the five-item short versions of the *Need for Cognition* (NFC) and *Faith in Intuition* (FI) scales taken from Study 2 by Epstein, Pacini, Denes-Raj, and Heier (1996) in order to tap into participants' inclination toward analytic and intuitive thought, respectively. Participants rated their agreement with short statements (example NFC item: "*I prefer complex to simple problems*"; example FI item: "*I believe in trusting my hunches*") on a scale from 1 ("*completely disagree*") to 5 ("*completely agree*"). The mean rating on the five items of each respective scale was used as the indicator of participants' analytic and intuitive thinking disposition.

Besides the individual analytic thinking indicators, in some of the analyses below, I examined whether analytic thinking was the mutual correlate and mediator of the relationship between probabilistic reasoning biases, biased evaluation of evidence, and ESBs. For this purpose, I used an analytic thinking composite score derived from the principal component analysis with cognitive ability, cognitive reflection, scientific reasoning, numeracy, and the two thinking

dispositions indicators. The analysis suggested a single component with an eigenvalue greater than one and 42% of the explained variance with high loadings of all six analytic thinking indicators (as could be expected, the loading was negative for intuitive thinking disposition).

Political liberalism and strength of religious faith:

As part of the demographic questionnaire, participants were asked two questions pertaining to their political leaning (“*Where would you put yourself on a political spectrum from conservative to liberal?*”) and the strength of their religious faith (“*How important is religion in your daily life?*”). Participants responded to each question using a seven-point rating scale. Higher ratings reflected stronger political liberalism and religious faith. The descriptive statistics for the two worldview indicators are presented in Table 3.

Procedure

The study was run as an online survey created in Qualtrics software. Participants were first presented with an informed consent form. After that, the study was split into two blocks, and participants were instructed that they could take a break between the blocks to reduce fatigue given the length of the study. The first block consisted of heuristics and biases problems and the second one contained analytic thinking indicators and the ESB questionnaire. Prior to each type of reasoning task, participants were presented with thorough instructions to familiarize them with the task at hand. The materials included two additional short measures – the self-report Subjective Numeracy Scale with three items and the 27-item Money Choice Questionnaire. These were included as part of a different research study (Bačová & Šrol, 2021) and thus will not be analyzed here. The two blocks and all the measures within the block were in random order. At the end of the study, participants filled in their basic demographic information and answered the questions about their political and religious affiliation.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The results are organized into several sections. First, I conducted a confirmatory factor analysis to test the psychometric structure of the refined 28-item ESB questionnaire obtained in Study 1. Then, I explored the individual differences in the endorsement of ESBs and susceptibility to cognitive biases through correlations with analytic thinking indicators. Correlations between probabilistic reasoning biases, belief bias in syllogistic reasoning, and unwarranted beliefs were

then examined to determine which of the cognitive biases were most closely related to the endorsement of paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific claims. To ascertain the role of worldview indicators in the endorsement of ESBs, I also included the associations with strength of religious faith and political liberalism. Finally, I conducted three regression analyses to see whether probabilistic reasoning biases and belief bias in syllogistic reasoning predicted the endorsement of paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific beliefs over and above analytic thinking indicators, and worldview and demographic covariates.

Confirmatory factor analysis of the refined ESB questionnaire

First, I performed a confirmatory factor analysis with DWLS estimation on the 28-item ESB questionnaire to test its psychometric structure and to see whether the results were compatible with the findings obtained in Study 1. The questionnaire with 28 refined items loading on three factors showed a good fit to the data, $\chi^2(347) = 700.94$, $p < .001$, CFI = .978, TLI = .976, RMSEA = .051. Crucially, the fit of the three-factor model was better than the fit of the one-factor model where all the items were loaded on a single latent dimension, $\chi^2(350) = 919.69$, $p < .001$, CFI = .964, TLI = .961, RMSEA = .064, and the chi-square difference test showed that this difference between the models was highly significant, $\chi^2_{difference}(3) = 218.75$, $p < .001$. The standardized factor loadings, along with mean ratings and endorsement rates for all the ESB questionnaire items, can be found in Table 1. In the analyses reported below, I use average ratings for the three subscales, i.e., paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific beliefs, as well as a composite average of all 28-item ratings ($M = 2.32$, $SD = 0.69$, $\alpha = .93$) as an indicator of the general propensity to endorse ESBs.

Correlations between the endorsement of ESBs, probabilistic reasoning biases, belief bias in syllogistic reasoning, and analytic thinking indicators

Correlations between ESBs, cognitive biases, and analytic thinking indicators are presented in Table 4. Focusing first on the ESBs, the endorsement of one type of unwarranted belief was strongly related to endorsement of the other beliefs (all r 's $> .65$), suggesting a large degree of common overlap, as a lot of previous research has found (Darwin, Neave, & Holmes, 2011; Lobato et al., 2014; Pennycook, Cheyne, et al., 2015). Crucially, the composite epistemically suspect belief score was moderately correlated with all of the analytic thinking indicators. Higher cognitive ability, cognitive reflection, analytic thinking disposition, and numeracy were all associated with lower endorsement of ESBs (Pennycook, Cheyne, et al., 2015; Stanovich et al., 2016). Moreover, in line with a recent study by Čavoјová et al. (2020), scientific reasoning

ability was substantially negatively associated with the composite ESB score. Intuitive thinking disposition, on the other hand, was positively correlated with the acceptance of ESBs (Lindeman, 2011; Swami, Voracek, Stieger, Tran, & Furnham, 2014). The correlations with the individual analytic thinking indicators, as well as with the analytic thinking composite score, were remarkably similar when considered separately for paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific beliefs.

Next, I examined the correlations between susceptibility to probabilistic reasoning biases, belief bias in syllogistic reasoning, and the endorsement of paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific claims (Table 4). Surprisingly, conjunction fallacy, perhaps the most studied probabilistic reasoning bias in relation to the endorsement of ESBs (Brotherton & French, 2014; Rogers et al., 2009, 2016), showed the weakest correlation with the composite belief score, and correlated significantly only with the acceptance of paranormal and conspiracy beliefs. All other probabilistic reasoning biases, as well as syllogistic belief bias, were significantly related to the higher endorsement of each type of unwarranted belief. This is consistent with the two dominant accounts of the adoption and maintenance of such beliefs – selective bias and biased probability judgment hypothesis (e.g. Dagnall et al., 2007).

Table 4. Correlations between ESBs, bias susceptibility, and analytic thinking indicators

	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.	8.	9.	10.	11.	12.	13.	14.	15.	16.
1. Paranormal beliefs	1															
2. Conspiracy beliefs	.66	1														
3. Pseudoscientific beliefs	.66	.65	1													
4. ESB composite	(.90)	(.88)	(.85)	1												
5. Syllogistic belief bias	.32	.32	.34	.37	1											
6. Ratio bias	.20	.21	.20	.23	.24	1										
7. Conjunction fallacy	.17	.10	.10	.14	.28	.16	1									
8. Base-rate neglect	.23	.21	.22	.25	.35	.20	.39	1								
9. Gambler's fallacy	.38	.33	.39	.42	.35	.26	.21	.34	1							
10. Probabilistic biases	.35	.31	.32	.37	.46	(.56)	(.69)	(.77)	(.63)	1						
11. Cognitive ability	-.24	-.22	-.26	-.27	-.36	-.19	-.18	-.20	-.28	-.31	1					
12. Cognitive reflection	-.35	-.27	-.33	-.36	-.48	-.29	-.25	-.26	-.44	-.45	.48	1				
13. Scientific reasoning	-.35	-.32	-.36	-.39	-.51	-.23	-.24	-.28	-.35	-.40	.38	.49	1			
14. Analytic thinking disp.	-.20	-.19	-.21	-.22	-.25	-.11	-.12	-.20	-.21	-.24	.16	.20	.22	1		
15. Intuitive thinking disp.	.36	.28	.26	.35	.29	.11	.20	.18	.17	.25	-.19	-.25	-.25	-.04	1	
16. Numeracy	-.26	-.23	-.26	-.29	-.36	-.24	-.27	-.33	-.34	-.44	.40	.50	.38	.18	-.17	1
17. Analytic thinking comp.	-.44	-.38	-.43	-.48	-.59	-.32	-.33	-.37	-.47	-.56	(.71)	(.81)	(.74)	(.38)	(-.38)	(.72)

Note. Correlations are based on 397 observations. Correlations in parentheses indicate part-whole relationships. Correlations of $r > .10$ are significant at $p < .05$, $r > .13$ are significant at $p < .01$, and $r > .17$ are significant at $p < .001$. Correlations that appear in bold are significant ($p < .05$). ESB: epistemically suspect belief. Analytic thinking composite score is derived from the principal component analysis with all analytic thinking indicators (see method section).

Lastly, I scrutinize the correlations between analytic thinking indicators and susceptibility to cognitive biases. Looking at Table 4, we can see that all the correlations between analytic thinking indicators and probabilistic reasoning biases and belief bias in syllogistic reasoning were significant and in the expected direction. Thinking disposition variables and cognitive ability were moderately related to all cognitive bias variables, whereas cognitive reflection, scientific reasoning, and numeracy all showed quite strong correlations in this regard, consistent with previous research (e.g., Čavojová et al., 2020; Šrol & De Neys, 2020; Stanovich et al., 2016). Importantly, the correlations between analytic thinking indicators and cognitive biases were largely consistent when considering each of the heuristics and biases tasks separately. A more thorough examination of analytic thinking indicators as predictors of the susceptibility to cognitive biases is presented in Section C of the Supplementary Material. Crucially, while the probabilistic reasoning biases and belief bias in syllogistic reasoning were shown to correlate with the endorsement of paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific beliefs, all of the cognitive biases and epistemically suspect belief variables were also substantially correlated with analytic thinking indicators.

Correlations between political liberalism, strength of religious faith, and endorsement of ESBs

Both political liberalism and strength of religious faith approximately moderately correlated with the endorsement of various ESBs. As expected, political liberalism was negatively related to the endorsement of paranormal ($r = -.13, p = .010$), conspiracy ($r = -.23, p < .001$), and pseudoscientific beliefs ($r = -.29, p < .001$), and showed a moderate negative correlation with the overall epistemically suspect belief composite ($r = -.24, p < .001$). The strength of religious faith, on the other hand, was positively linked to the acceptance of paranormal ($r = .28, p < .001$), conspiracy ($r = .22, p < .001$), and pseudoscientific claims ($r = .40, p < .001$), as well as to the epistemically suspect belief composite score ($r = .33, p < .001$). Overall, these results are consistent with the line of research which shows that one's worldviews, so-called cultural cognition, play an important role in the endorsement of ESBs (Kahan, Jenkins-Smith, & Braman, 2011; Lewandowsky et al., 2013).

Analytic thinking, belief bias in syllogistic reasoning, and probabilistic reasoning biases as predictors of ESBs

Both belief bias in syllogistic reasoning and probabilistic reasoning biases were correlated with all three types of ESBs. They also showed substantial relationships with the indicators of analytic thinking, i.e., cognitive ability, cognitive reflection, numeracy, scientific reasoning, and thinking dispositions. Therefore, to establish whether the two cognitive bias paradigms independently predict the endorsement of ESBs, or if their relationships can be fully explained by analytic thinking or other (worldview or demographic) variables, I conducted three regression analyses, one for each type of ESB⁶. In each regression model, both belief bias in syllogistic reasoning and probabilistic reasoning biases were included as predictors of the respective type of ESB along with the analytic thinking composite score. Moreover, all the models included age, gender, political liberalism, and strength of religious faith as predictors. Besides the common regression statistics, the analyses below also report general dominance (GD) statistics for the predictors extracted from *R* package *yhat* (Nimon et al., 2020). These can be used to compare the relative importance of individual predictors in the regression, as the general dominance expresses the contribution of each predictor in the regression model to the explained variance in the outcome variable (R^2).

The three regression analyses for paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific beliefs are shown in Table 5. As can be seen from the table, analytic thinking predicted the endorsement of each type of ESB to a relatively similar extent (β 's between .20 – .28) and contributed 7–10% of the explained variance in the paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific beliefs. However, after accounting for the other predictors in the regression, the moderate correlation between belief bias in syllogistic reasoning and the endorsement of ESBs was almost completely partialled out. That is, belief bias in syllogistic reasoning was not a significant

⁶ Another approach for testing the role of two cognitive bias predictors in the endorsement of paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific beliefs would be to conduct parallel mediation analyses with analytic thinking as the predictor of the three types of ESB along with belief bias in syllogistic reasoning and probabilistic reasoning biases as mediators of this relationship. These analyses are not included in the main manuscript, as the use of mediation analyses might give the readers a false impression about the causality of the associations presented here (mediation models could indicate causal relationships between the predictor, mediator, and outcome variables that cannot be established given the present cross-sectional design). However, for interested readers, the mediation analyses are included in Section G of the Supplementary Material. It is important to note that the results of the supplementary analyses are qualitatively no different from those presented below.

independent predictor of the endorsement of paranormal or conspiracy beliefs; however, it did predict pseudoscientific beliefs even after controlling for other factors. The dominance analysis suggested that approximately 4.5% of the endorsement of pseudoscientific beliefs could be explained by the individual differences in susceptibility to belief bias in syllogistic reasoning.

Table 5. Summary of the regression analysis with predictors of paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific beliefs

Predictors	<i>b</i>	95% CI	β	95% CI	partial <i>r</i>	GD
<i>Paranormal beliefs</i>						
Intercept	1.76**	[1.29, 2.22]				
Analytic thinking	-0.23**	[-0.33, -0.13]	-.28	[-.40, -.15]	-.23	.101
Syllogistic belief bias	0.03	[-0.02, 0.07]	.07	[-.04, .18]	.06	.038
Probabilistic biases	0.09*	[0.00, 0.18]	.11	[.01, .22]	.10	.053
Age	-0.00	[-0.01, 0.00]	-.02	[-.11, .07]	-.02	.000
Gender	0.25**	[0.10, 0.39]	.14	[.06, .22]	.16	.025
Political liberalism	-0.02	[-0.07, 0.04]	-.03	[-.12, .07]	-.03	.006
Religious faith	0.09**	[0.04, 0.13]	.19	[.09, .29]	.21	.049
$F(7,388) = 20.74, p < .001, R^2 = .27, 95\% \text{ CI } [.21, .36]$						
<i>Conspiracy beliefs</i>						
Intercept	2.66 **	[2.15, 3.1]				
Analytic thinking	-0.17**	[-0.28, -0.06]	-.20	[-.33, -.07]	-.17	.069
Syllogistic belief bias	0.04	[-0.01, 0.09]	.10	[-.02, 0.22]	.09	.039
Probabilistic biases	0.11*	[0.02, 0.20]	.13	[.03, .24]	.12	.043
Age	-0.01	[-0.01, 0.00]	-.09	[-.18, .01]	-.10	.006
Gender	-0.09	[-0.25, 0.07]	-.05	[-.14, .04]	-.05	.002
Political liberalism	0.06**	[-0.14, -0.22]	-0.13	[-.23, -.03]	-.14	.028
Religious faith	-0.08**	[0.01, 0.11]	0.12	[.02, .23]	.13	.026
$F(7,388) = 15.01, p < .001, R^2 = .21, 95\% \text{ CI } [.16, .31]$						
<i>Pseudoscientific beliefs</i>						
Intercept	1.91**	[1.54, 2.28]				
Analytic thinking	-0.16**	[-0.23, -0.08]	-.23	[-.33, -.12]	-.21	.085
Syllogistic belief bias	0.03*	[-0.00, 0.07]	.10	[-.00, .21]	.10	.044
Probabilistic biases	0.04	[-0.03, 0.11]	.06	[-.05, .17]	.06	.039
Age	0.01**	[0.01, 0.01]	.17	[.09, .24]	.20	.035
Gender	0.19**	[0.07, 0.31]	.13	[.05, .21]	.16	.019
Political liberalism	-0.08**	[-0.13, -0.04]	-.16	[-.25, -.08]	-.19	.046
Religious faith	0.10**	[0.08, 0.13]	.29	[.21, .36]	.33	.106
$F(7,388) = 32.92, p < .001, R^2 = .37, 95\% \text{ CI } [.31, .45]$						

Note. The table contains unstandardized (*b*) and standardized (β) regression coefficients along with their 95% confidence intervals, Pearson's partial correlations, and general dominance (GD) statistics extracted from *R* package *yhat* (Nimon et al., 2020) for the predictors of ESBs. Gender was coded as 1 = "male", 2 = "female". Confidence intervals are based on 5,000 bootstrap samples. $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$; *** $p < .001$

The probabilistic reasoning biases, on the other hand, contributed around 5% of the explained variance in paranormal ($\beta = .11$) and conspiracy belief ($\beta = .13$) endorsement, even after controlling for the effect of belief bias in syllogistic reasoning, analytic thinking, age, gender, political liberalism, and religious faith. This shows strong evidence for the role of biased perception of randomness in the endorsement of the two types of ESB. Importantly, probabilistic reasoning biases did not independently predict the endorsement of pseudoscientific beliefs. Although the model for pseudoscientific beliefs without demographic and worldview predictors did show susceptibility to probabilistic reasoning biases as a significant predictor ($\beta = .12$, 95% CI [.01, .23]), this effect was partialled out after the inclusion of other factors.

Turning to the role of worldview and demographic factors (see Table 5), as could be expected, both political liberalism and religious faith showed substantial relationships with the endorsement of various ESBs. As previously observed, participants with a more liberal leaning held fewer conspiracy and pseudoscientific beliefs (e.g., Lewandowsky, Gignac, et al., 2013; Ståhl & van Prooijen, 2018). People with stronger religious faith endorsed more ESBs in general. This effect was, however, particularly pronounced for pseudoscientific beliefs ($\beta = .29$) where religious faith actually showed up as the strongest predictor in the present analysis, contributing more than 10% to the explained variance (see also, Lobato et al., 2014). Consistent with the correlation analysis presented above, age positively predicted the extent to which people endorsed pseudoscientific beliefs (see also Majima, 2015). Concerning gender, women held more paranormal and pseudoscientific beliefs in comparison with men, which has also been documented in some other studies (e.g., Lobato et al. 2014; Čavojová et al. 2019). Together, the predictors explained 27% of the variance in paranormal beliefs, 21% of the variance in conspiracy beliefs, and 37% of the variance in pseudoscientific beliefs, suggesting both model stability and that other potential variables may play an important role in the endorsement of such beliefs.

GENERAL DISCUSSION

The results presented here were obtained via a comprehensive investigation of the individual differences in ESBs and offer important novel evidence regarding the role of susceptibility to cognitive biases in the adoption and maintenance of unwarranted beliefs. For some time now, it has been recognized that certain ESBs may arise as a consequence of specific probabilistic

reasoning biases and biases in belief formation and the evaluation of evidence (Blackmore & Trościanko, 1985; Dagnall et al., 2007). In line with this theoretical proposition, the present results show that the susceptibility to probabilistic reasoning biases predicted paranormal and conspiracy beliefs even after accounting for a wide range of analytic thinking indicators, worldview variables, and demographic factors. While belief bias in syllogistic reasoning, as one facet of the biased evaluation of evidence, only significantly predicted pseudoscientific beliefs independently of other factors, it was shown to substantially correlate with the endorsement of all three types of ESBs. Also important is the finding that analytic thinking was a consistent independent predictor of the endorsement of paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific beliefs. Finally, two worldview variables – political liberalism and the strength of religious faith – were also shown to substantially contribute to the extent to which people endorsed unwarranted beliefs. The present results, therefore, extend the previous findings on individual differences in ESBs in several important ways.

First, there is a solid line of research showing that some probabilistic reasoning biases are more prevalent among those who endorse paranormal and conspiracy beliefs (Brotherton & French, 2014; Dagnall et al., 2007, 2014; Rogers et al., 2009, 2016). The correlation analyses in Study 1 and 2 consistently showed that all the probabilistic reasoning biases examined here were correlated with the endorsement of paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific beliefs. The only exception was conjunction fallacy, which was not associated with conspiracy beliefs in Study 1 and only showed a marginally significant correlation with pseudoscientific beliefs in Study 2 (I return to this point below). Thus, the present results show that the link between ESBs and probabilistic reasoning biases is not specific to any particular bias, such as conjunction fallacy, (e.g., Rogers et al., 2009, 2016, 2017) or misperception of chance (see Dagnall et al., 2007, 2014). Rather, it seems to reflect a more general tendency toward biased reasoning with probabilistic content that might make some people more prone to adopt paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific beliefs.

Importantly, the analyses here go a step further by showing that people prone to various biases in probabilistic reasoning endorse more paranormal, conspiracy beliefs, and to some extent, pseudoscientific beliefs, even after the differences in analytic thinking, worldview variables, and demographic factors are accounted for. This is consistent with the theoretical and empirical work showing that the perception that unrelated or random events and stimuli are co-occurrent or causally related might be a determining factor in the adoption of paranormal and conspiracy beliefs (van der Wal et al., 2018; van Prooijen, Douglas, & Inocencio, 2018). While

pseudoscientific beliefs are usually not examined in this context, there is some evidence for the role of causal illusion – the tendency to perceive a causal relationship between non-contingent events – in the endorsement of such beliefs (Torres et al., 2020). Although probabilistic reasoning biases did not manifest here to predict pseudoscientific beliefs once worldview and demographic variables were accounted for, they were still substantially correlated with the endorsement of such beliefs. This suggests that while biased probabilistic reasoning may not be as crucial a factor in the adoption and maintenance of pseudoscientific beliefs as it is in paranormal and conspiracy beliefs, various systematic errors in probabilistic reasoning may at least partially contribute to the tendency to endorse pseudoscience (see also Torres et al., 2020).

Surprisingly, the tendency to commit conjunction fallacy, which is one of the most consistent probabilistic reasoning bias correlates of paranormal and conspiracy beliefs (Brotherton & French, 2014; Prike et al., 2017; Rogers et al., 2009, 2016, 2017), was shown here to have the weakest association with ESBs in general, and its correlations with conspiracy and paranormal beliefs were modest at best. This inconsistency with regard to previous findings on conjunction fallacy could be partially explained by the differences in response format for the items used to measure this cognitive bias. In the present study, participants were asked to select between two options (single-feature option and conjunction of two features). Previous researchers (Brotherton & French, 2014; Rogers et al., 2009) asked participants to rate the relative chances of three possible options (two single-event and one conjunction option) occurring, which could perhaps evoke a somewhat lower tendency to commit a conjunction fallacy. Also, as shown by Rogers et al., (2016, 2017), the extent of the relationship between the conjunction fallacy and the endorsement of paranormal beliefs may vary depending on the type of conjunction error and on the facet of paranormal belief being investigated, e.g., extrasensory perception, belief in life after death, or psychokinesis. Similarly, Prike et al. (2017) found that the tendency to commit a conjunction fallacy is strongest among people who believe they have personally experienced paranormal phenomena, such as seeing UFOs in the sky. Since the paranormal beliefs investigated here did not include some of these previously studied categories of paranormal phenomena, this could have weakened the relationship between the conjunction fallacy and the endorsement of paranormal beliefs in the present study.

Besides probabilistic reasoning biases, belief bias in syllogistic reasoning also moderately correlated with all three types of ESB. However, in the regression models in which analytic thinking, worldview variables, and demographic factors were included, syllogistic belief bias was not an independent predictor of paranormal or conspiracy beliefs, predicting only the

endorsement of pseudoscientific beliefs. It is, however, very likely that the effect of belief bias in syllogistic reasoning was largely partialled out because of the substantial association with lower analytic thinking ($r = -.59$). Specifically, belief bias was shown to be especially strongly correlated with two analytic thinking indicators – cognitive reflection and scientific reasoning. This is not surprising, as both of these variables tap into dimensions which are also related to the unbiased evaluation of information, with cognitive reflection as the tendency to reflect on and suppress inappropriate immediate intuitive responses (Baron et al., 2015), and scientific reasoning as the ability to objectively evaluate the quality of scientific evidence (Drummond & Fischhoff, 2017a).

Be that as it may, the correlations are substantial, but the lack of independent predictive power of belief bias in syllogistic reasoning in the endorsement of paranormal and conspiracy beliefs in the present study begs further research into the issue. While belief bias, as one of the facets of biased evaluation of evidence, is not commonly studied as a predictor of ESBs, there are theoretical grounds for expecting it to contribute in this way. It has been well documented that people's perception of and stance on controversial issues, such as climate change, vaccination, or genetically modified foods, is largely shaped by their existing beliefs and attitudes (Kahan et al., 2011; Lewandowsky et al., 2013). It is conceivable that information evaluation biases underlie the rejection of information on which there is a scientific consensus but which also goes against the person's prior beliefs. Such biases may also lead to a greater acceptance of claims that correspond to the person's existing worldview. While the present evidence clearly shows that people who endorse paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific beliefs are more susceptible to belief bias in the syllogistic reasoning task, the primary cause seems to be their lower levels of analytic thinking. Perhaps, further research into this issue could examine other facets of the biased evaluation of evidence that have previously been shown to predict ESBs but have yet to be investigated while taking into account the individual differences in analytic thinking, such as myside bias in an argument evaluation task (Svedholm & Lindeman, 2013) or the tendency toward actively open-minded thinking (Rizeq et al., 2020; I return to this point below).

It should also be noted that although probabilistic reasoning biases and syllogistic belief bias, as one aspect of the biased evaluation of evidence, are discussed here as two relatively independent cognitive bias paradigms in relation to ESBs, it is likely that their role in the adoption and maintenance of those beliefs is closely intertwined. As already mentioned, in both these paradigms normative reasoning depends on one's ability and motivation to think

analytically (Stanovich et al., 2016). That is why both probabilistic reasoning biases and belief bias in syllogistic reasoning were strongly correlated with analytic thinking indicators in the present study. However, even after controlling for analytic thinking, the two paradigms were still significantly associated ($r = .20$; see mediation analyses in Section G in the Supplementary Material), which shows that the biased evaluation of evidence and probabilistic reasoning have more commonalities than just mutual dependence on analytic thinking. Indeed, probabilistic reasoning biases can also be explained as stemming from the processes involved in the biased evaluation of evidence, such as various sampling effects (Fiedler, 2000)⁷. It may therefore be impossible to completely distinguish between the two accounts explaining the adoption and endorsement of ESBs. People who are susceptible to biased probabilistic reasoning may be more prone to endorse such beliefs because they tend to think random events occur together or even that they are causally related (van der Wal et al., 2018; van Prooijen, Douglas, & Inocencio, 2018). Biased evaluation of evidence would, however, likely interact with this process, guiding people's attention to observations that fit their existing (or forming) worldview, and help them explain away the evidence opposing their beliefs on the grounds that it is weak, unreliable, or logically fallacious (e.g., Lewandowsky & Oberauer, 2016). While this study has taken the first step in disentangling these two complementary cognitive bias accounts of the adoption and endorsement of ESBs by distinguishing them from their shared analytic thinking component, future research will be needed to examine how these processes interact in predicting the endorsement of paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific beliefs.

As noted above the evidence shows a strong relationship between the extent to which people endorse ESBs and their preexisting attitudes and worldviews. In line with that, it was observed here that political liberalism related negatively to the endorsement of conspiracy and pseudoscientific beliefs, while strength of religious faith positively predicted all ESBs. Previous research shows that political conservatism and/or strength of religious faith are related to conspiracy beliefs and conspiracist ideation, as well as the rejection of some scientific findings, such as those on human evolution, stem cell research, or climate change (e.g., Drummond & Fischhoff, 2017b; Lewandowsky, Gignac, et al., 2013; Ståhl & van Prooijen, 2018). Similarly, paranormal beliefs are traditionally associated with religious faith; indeed, traditional religious beliefs (belief in the devil, God, or heaven) are sometimes conceptualized as part of paranormal beliefs (e.g., Tobacyk, 2004). Interestingly, in the present study, the

⁷ The author would like to thank Shira Elqayam for this point.

strength of religious faith was shown to be the strongest predictor of the endorsement of pseudoscientific beliefs, even when cognitive biases, analytic thinking, and demographic variables were accounted for. This is in line with the findings of Lobato et al. (2014), who identified religious affiliation as one of the strongest independent predictors of belief in pseudoscience. They attributed this to the fact that their pseudoscientific belief measure included statements that contradicted core Christian beliefs in that they referred to the theory of evolution or the age of Earth for example. This could partially explain the link between strength of religious faith and pseudoscientific beliefs in the present study since the pseudoscientific belief subscale included items relating to the theory of human evolution. Nonetheless, the independent predictive effect of worldview indicators on the endorsement of ESBs underlines the previously argued point that people's evaluation of evidence relating to some ESBs may be influenced more by the mechanism of motivated cognition (e.g., Lewandowsky & Oberauer, 2016) than by logical analysis or critical thinking.

But the results also showed that analytic thinking was a substantial predictor of the endorsement of ESBs, even after accounting for individual differences in susceptibility to cognitive biases, worldview indicators, and demographic factors. While all analytic thinking indicators were significantly associated with the endorsement of paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific beliefs, particularly pronounced correlations were found with intuitive thinking disposition, cognitive reflection, and scientific reasoning. Intuitive thinking disposition and cognitive reflection – i.e., the tendency to reflect upon one's intuitive processes – can be conceptualized as the two key basic cognitive mechanisms behind succumbing to ESBs (Pennycook, Fugelsang, et al., 2015; Risen, 2016). Intuitive thinkers who when reasoning tend to rely on intuitive heuristic processes – such as those related to the biased probabilistic reasoning and evaluation of evidence examined in the present study – are known to more uncritically accept various suspect beliefs without further reflection (Lindeman & Aarnio, 2006, 2007; Svedholm & Lindeman, 2013). By contrast, people high in cognitive reflection have a better chance of realizing the faultiness of the claims that often underpin such beliefs which, although perhaps intuitively appealing, do not stand up to scrutiny via analytic reasoning.

Scientific reasoning is substantially associated with the endorsement of paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific beliefs, likely because it represents the mindware that is central to the adoption of such beliefs (Čavojová, Šrol, & Ballová Mikušková, 2020; Čavojová, Šrol, & Jurkovič, 2020). This is because many of the claims underpinning paranormal and

pseudoscientific beliefs have either already been directly disproven by science or cannot be empirically tested because they are based on “irrefutable” hypotheses (e.g., Hines, 2002). Likewise, conspiracy theories are usually not subject to scientific inquiry because they do not possess the qualities embedded in scientific theories, such as those related to consistency, coherency, and falsifiability (Lewandowsky, Gignac, et al., 2013). People with better scientific reasoning mindware are more likely to be aware of these shortcomings and the faulty evidence underpinning many ESBs and so are more likely to reject those beliefs. Also, previous studies have shown that knowledge and acceptance of scientific facts and trust in science is related to some epistemically suspect claims (Fasce & Picó, 2019b, 2019a; Majima, 2015). Therefore, fostering scientific reasoning and positive attitudes toward science could constitute a way to counter the high prevalence of the ESBs that can currently be observed among the general population (e.g., Čavojová, Šrol, & Ballová Mikušková, 2020).

Besides examining the individual difference predictors of paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific beliefs, the present two studies produced some novel findings on the links between various types of ESB. In the research on unwarranted beliefs, substantial attention is being paid to the development of adequate measurement instruments (Brotherton et al., 2013; Fasce & Picó, 2019a; Rizeq et al., 2020). One of the reasons for this is that while ESBs are known to be culturally specific, researchers need measures that allow them to compare the results pertaining to those beliefs across countries (e.g., Bruder et al., 2013). The consistency of the psychometric properties of the questionnaire on ESBs was therefore tested on two samples – a Slovak sample recruited through social media queries (Study 1) and a predominately US and UK English-speaking Prolific sample (Study 2). This lends further credence to the generalizability of the results. The confirmatory factor analysis across both studies showed that ESBs are best conceived of as three separate but very strongly correlated factors. This is in line with much of the previous research, which observed moderate to strong correlations between various types of ESBs (e.g., Lobato et al. 2014; Stanovich et al. 2016; Bensley et al. 2019; Fasce and Picó 2019a; Čavojová et al. 2020). Moreover, in a recent study, Rizeq et al. (2020) similarly showed that contaminated mindware is best characterized by a hierarchical structure with three general factors for paranormal, conspiracy, and anti-science beliefs, and four specific factors representing various facets of paranormal beliefs (e.g., superstition, spiritualism). The findings of the present research are thus consistent with their results regarding the general factors underlying the endorsement of ESBs. It should be noted that in the present study I attempted to create a questionnaire that would reliably measure the

three main dimensions of ESBs, but I did not strive to include specific factors representing various facets of those beliefs. However, when analyzing larger pools of paranormal (Tobacyk, 2004), conspiracy (Ballová Mikušková, 2017; Brotherton et al., 2013), or pseudoscientific (Fasce & Picó, 2019a) beliefs, specific facets would certainly be expected to emerge.

Before I conclude, I would like to mention several limitations of the present research. The proportion of variance explained in ESBs by cognitive biases, analytic thinking indicators, worldview variables, and demographic factors was relatively high, but the models still showed a lot of potential for improvement. It is noteworthy that a recent study by Rizeq et al. (2020) identified an important independent predictor of ESBs that was not included in the present study – actively open-minded thinking. The actively open-minded thinking disposition is related to analytic thinking indicators, such as the lower intuitive and higher analytic thinking disposition (Svedholm-Häkkinen & Lindeman, 2017) or cognitive reflection (e.g., Rizeq et al., 2020), but it represents a separate construct that taps into the tendency to consider the evidence even if it opposes one's beliefs. In fact, it may be seen as a facet of the unbiased evaluation of evidence, i.e., the tendency not to search for evidence or reach conclusions merely on the basis of whether they fit one's existing beliefs (Baron et al., 2015). Examining the actively open-minded thinking disposition and measuring probabilistic reasoning biases and analytic thinking indicators could potentially help to further disentangle the various aspects of biased reasoning processes that contribute to the endorsement of ESBs. Furthermore, the present study focused on cognitive predictors, but the unexplained variance in ESBs could also relate to other types of variables previously shown to consistently predict the endorsement of paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific beliefs. These include personality variables, such as extraversion, neuroticism, paranoid ideation, or schizotypy (e.g., Darwin et al., 2011; Lobato et al., 2014). The inclusion of such personality predictors would likely have led to a substantial improvement in the explained variance of the mediation models.

To conclude, in the present study I examined individual difference predictors of ESBs, focusing specifically on the role of the susceptibility to cognitive biases in the endorsement of such beliefs. The results showed substantial correlations between probabilistic reasoning biases, belief bias in syllogistic reasoning, and the endorsement of paranormal, conspiracy, and pseudoscientific beliefs. In spite of that, only probabilistic reasoning biases predicted the endorsement of paranormal beliefs, conspiracy beliefs, and to some extent, pseudoscientific beliefs when analytic thinking, worldview indicators, and demographic variables were accounted for. The effect of belief bias in syllogistic reasoning on the endorsement of ESBs,

on the other hand, was largely restricted to pseudoscientific beliefs. Thus, biased probabilistic reasoning could constitute a common mechanism that makes some people more likely to interpret random or co-occurring events as being meaningfully related and to subsequently adopt paranormal, conspiracy, and/or pseudoscientific explanations to account for these tentative connections (Torres et al., 2020; van der Wal et al., 2018; van Prooijen et al., 2018). However, further research will be needed to disentangle the interplay between analytic thinking and the mechanisms responsible for the biased evaluation of evidence that may lead to the tendency to selectively attend to information that is consistent with one's prior beliefs (Čavojová et al., 2018; Macpherson & Stanovich, 2007), thus making it extremely difficult to change people's extant attitudes.

DECLARATION OF INTEREST

The author declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

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